

EFFECTIVENESS OF GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING PROGRAMS IN MANAGING INDISCIPLINE CASES IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN BURETI SUB-COUNTY, KERICHO COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract:

There are many public secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County. Most of the students in these secondary schools have been facing cases of indiscipline for many years and these cases seem to be increasing as years go by causing a lot of concern to the school management, parents and the communities at large. Although counseling is offered in the secondary schools, there has been a rise in indiscipline cases at an alarming rate as experienced especially in 2016. The purpose of this study was to examine the effectiveness of guidance and counselling programs on managing indiscipline cases in secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County, Kericho County, Kenya. The study was guided by the following specific objectives; to investigate the competence of teachers in providing guidance and counselling programs in secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County and to establish the attitude of students and teachers on guidance and counselling programs in secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County. The theoretical framework adopted by the study was the Social Learning theory by Albert Bandura (1977) and Operant Conditioning theory by B.F. Skinner (1948). The Social Learning and Operant Conditioning theories were adopted because they help to change the behavior of the students and thus help to reduce indiscipline cases in schools. The target population comprised 52 public secondary schools, 52 head /deputy head teachers, 52 teacher counsellors, 540 teachers and 10532 students. Out of all these, a sample of 10 secondary schools, 10 head/deputy head teachers, 10 teacher counsellors, 108 teachers and 2106 students were selected through the Purposive sampling technique. Stratified

Sampling technique was used to select the secondary schools that were studied whereby the strata consisted of mixed day boarding school, mixed day school, boys' only boarding school, girls' only boarding school and girls only day schools. The instruments that were used to collect the data for the study were questionnaires for head/deputies, teacher counsellors, teachers and students and interview schedules were administered to the teacher counsellors and to deputy head teachers. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and tested using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient using Statistical Package of Social Sciences. Questionnaires were analyzed using summary tables for the purpose of data presentation and interpretation. The expected findings were used to guide policy makers in providing guidance and counselling programs in secondary schools. These findings will be useful in the schools.

Keywords: guidance, counselling programs, managing indiscipline, secondary schools, Kenya

1. Background of the Study

Guidance and counseling programs have been there from time immemorial (Chai, 2000). In the olden days, our great grandparents used to guide and counsel their children using traditional means, for example using stories, proverbs, and sayings in order to deter the youth from committing crimes or going against the rules and regulations of the society. Taboos and cultural practices were also followed in order to instill discipline (Denga, 2001).

At the turn of 20th century, school counsellors in Africa did not exist but rather, teachers used a few minutes of their day to provide students with vocational guidance (Bower & Hatch, 2002). In the early 1900's, an influx of various types of students in the public schools occurred as a result of industrial revolution initiating the development of the school guidance movement (Gysbers, 2003).

Various government policy documents, since independence, like the Ominde report (1964), the Gachathi report (1976) and the Kamunge report (1988) have recognized the role of guidance and counselling in the administration and management of student discipline in Kenya.

It is believed that even the most primitive societies grew out of the necessity of guiding individual behaviour patterns in the interest of the group (Eyo, 2006). It was realized that indiscipline cases were increasing in schools, for example cases like fighting, theft, assault, vandalism, destruction of school property like stores, libraries

and other cases like harassments, riots, use of drugs and alcohol, rape, loss of lives through suicides and abortions.

The Ministry of Education(2002) recommended that guidance and counselling be taught using subjects like religious education, social education and ethics to enable the school promote the growth of self-discipline among students (Ministry of Education, 2009). Achoka (2007) explained that discipline problems may include destructions of school Property, laziness, drug abuse and boy-girl relationships and killings. In 1980 22(0.9%) of schools recorded cases of indiscipline in Kenya. This increased to 187(7.2%) in 1990 (Simotwa, 2007). These cases of indiscipline have continued to increase unabated to the extent that in 2001, the Ministry of Education (MOE) introduced guidelines on safety in schools.

The President appointed a taskforce headed by the then Director of Education whose mandate was to meet stakeholders, gather views and information and make recommendations in order to stem the culture of violence taking root in secondary schools in Kenya, Republic of Kenya(2001). Various reports of committees and taskforces recommended the use of guidance and Counselling in schools for management of student discipline (Edet, 2008).

Kamunge report of 1988, asserts that guidance and counselling of youth in secondary schools is essential in the identification of their interests, needs, correction and assistance to enable them face the realities of life. It further states that each school should have a mature teacher responsible for the co-ordination of guidance and counselling programs being carried out by other teachers (Kamunge report, 1988). The report of the taskforce on student indiscipline and unrest (GOK, 2001) recommended the strengthening of guidance and counselling division within the Ministry of Education to co-ordinate the activities of guidance and counselling in the country.

Stewart (2007) states that many students indiscipline problems that occur in secondary schools might not exist if guidance and counselling services were correctly offered. In 2014, two boys schools in Bureti Sub-County went on strike and students were sent home for two weeks (The Daily Nation, 10th April 2014).In 2015, another girl's school was reported to go on strike and burnt their dormitory (The Standard 24th October 2015).In 2015 again, another boys' school went on strike again ending up burning their bus and dormitory (Nation 15th July 2015). During the year 2016, many secondary schools witnessed a lot of destruction of property by students as they burnt their dormitories using petrol, causing loss of millions. Therefore as a result of the rising cases of indiscipline, there was need to scrutinize the effectiveness of guidance and counselling programs on management of indiscipline cases in secondary schools.

2. Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study was to establish the effectiveness of guidance and counselling programs on managing of indiscipline cases in secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County. Studies showed that Guidance and counselling programs offered in secondary schools have assisted to reduce indiscipline cases affecting students. These cases include destruction of school property, strikes, drug abuse, alcoholism, early teenage pregnancies, boy/girl relationships, suicides, abortions, dropping out of school, truancy, theft and many others. Although this is the case, there were a lot of indiscipline cases reported especially in the year 2016. However, this study sought to establish the effectiveness of guidance and counseling programs in secondary schools.

It has been proven that indiscipline cases in secondary schools have been on the rise, as reports indicate that in the year 2016 at least 106 secondary schools were burnt by students. Some of these secondary schools are; Langata High School in Nairobi whose dormitory was burnt on 25th July 2016 and the students lost all their personal items, St. Paul's Boys High School in Murang'a whose dormitory was burnt on 22nd July 2016, Londiani Boys High School who burnt their dormitory in April 2016, Wanguru Girls High School, Kiine Girls High School in Kirinyaga, Kapsera Mixed Secondary School were burnt on 26th July 2016, Narok Boys High School whose dormitory was burnt on 25th June 2016 and many more as reported by the standard newspaper of 27th July 2016.

This led to panic and tension among the parents and teachers of the secondary schools in the country and the situation had posed a significant concern among the stakeholders. Thus, the Cabinet Secretary for Education Dr. Fred Matiangi (2016) had to convene an urgent meeting for all head teachers to discuss the way forward in order to curb this menace which was affecting secondary schools. Properties worth millions of shillings were going down the drain because of indiscipline cases in the schools and the parents were to meet the cost of putting up new buildings. This study therefore sought to determine the effectiveness of guidance and counseling programs in management of indiscipline cases in secondary schools.

2.1 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the effectiveness of guidance and counselling programs on managing of indiscipline cases in secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County, Kericho County.

2.2 Objectives of the Study

This study was guided by the following specific objectives.

1. To examine whether teachers had sessions for guidance and counselling programs and if this had managed indiscipline cases in secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County.
2. To establish the attitude of teachers and students on guidance and counselling program and if this had managed indiscipline cases in secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County.

2.3 Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions.

1. Do teachers have sessions for guidance and counseling programs and has this managed indiscipline cases in secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County?
2. What was the attitude of teachers and students on counselling programs and their effect on management of indiscipline cases in secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County?

2.4 Justification of the Study

Indiscipline in secondary schools have been on the rise every year and 2016 was the worst as strikes were witnessed at an alarming rate with the students burning and destroying property worth millions of shillings like in Tengecha and Itierio boys in May and June 2016.

Sometimes these strikes endanger the lives of other students and make parents to suffer the consequences. This study has come at the time when indiscipline cases are on the rise.

The researcher therefore having witnessed the rise of these cases was left wondering whether guidance and counseling programs had any impact in schools and hence this study was conceived.

3. Methodology

The study utilised the mixed methods approach where both quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection were used. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The target population comprised 52 public secondary schools, 52 head /deputy head teachers, 52 teacher counsellors, 540 teachers and 10532 students. Out of all these, a sample of 10 secondary schools, 10 head/deputy head teachers, 10 teacher counsellors, 108 teachers and 2106 students were selected through Purposive

sampling technique. Stratified Sampling technique was used to select the secondary schools that were studied whereby the strata consisted of mixed day boarding schools, mixed day schools, boys' only boarding schools, girls' only boarding schools and girls only day schools. The instruments that were used to collect the data for the study were questionnaires for head/deputies, teacher counsellors, teachers and students and interviews were administered to the teacher counsellors and to deputy head teachers. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient using Statistical Package for Social Sciences. Questionnaires were analyzed using summary tables for the purpose of data presentation and interpretation. The expected findings will be used to guide policy makers in providing guidance and counselling programs in secondary schools. These findings will be useful in the schools. Validity and reliability of instruments were ascertained. After the test-retest, the instruments attained a reliability coefficient of 0.70 using the Cronbach alpha coefficient which was considered high enough to continue with data collection.

3.1 Study Findings

3.1.1 Sessions for guidance and counseling programs

In establishing whether teachers had sessions for guidance and counseling programs on management of indiscipline cases, the study sought to establish whether they had enough time, whether G&C was included in the timetable and the teacher counselors workload. The findings are summarized in Table 1 as follows:- 'A' stands for agree, 'U' is undecided and 'D' stands for disagree.

Table 1: Teacher Counsellors response on sessions allocated for Guidance and Counselling

Item	Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
G&C not included in the school table	1	16.7	-	-	5	83.3
Teachers do not have time for G & C because of workload	6	100	-	-	-	-

The study noted that majority (5) 83.3% of the teacher counsellors do not agree that the time allocated for guidance and counseling was adequate. The results agree with a previous study by Nyamwanja et. al (2013) in Bomet which established that the time allocated for guidance and counselling study was not adequate for the proper implementation of guidance and counseling program. The reasons given to support this

claim were that in most schools the G & C was not catered for in the school time table like the other examinable subjects and that the teachers' heavy teaching loads did not allow them to have sufficient time for guidance and counseling duties.

All the teacher counsellors agreed that they do not have time for the programme due to the workload of teaching. This implies that guidance and counseling in secondary schools could be compromised for teaching because of the struggle for schools to attain a set mean score. The findings concur with an earlier study by Mikaye (2012) which established that heavy workload for teacher counsellors was a great challenge that affected guidance and counseling in secondary schools in Kabondo.

Figure 1: Teachers response on time for G&C sessions not available for Guidance and Counselling

From the teachers' response, it was established that majority (4)71.3% agree that time was not available for guidance and counseling services. The findings concur with the results of the teacher counselors. This implies that availability of guidance and counseling was affected by time that was not available for conducting the sessions.

The students were also asked to give their ratings on whether guidance and counseling was included in the timetable and teacher counselors having time for counseling. The results are indicated in table 2

Table 2: Students' ratings on guidance and counseling time availability

Item	Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
Guidance and counseling are in school timetables	1588	100	-	-	-	-
Teachers do not use guidance and counseling because they are busy	1089	68.6	491	30.9	8	0.5

Table 2 reveals that all the students (188) 100% agree that guidance and counseling programs were not in the school timetable. Majority however indicated that teachers did not use guidance and counseling because they were busy. This implies that guidance and counseling program however how important it is, is compromised for other academic activities. Ngumo (2004) recommended that guidance and counseling be allocated adequate time in the school timetable to enable teachers to comfortably handle their clients without overstretching into their free time.

3.1.2 Attitude of teachers and students on guidance and counseling programs on management of indiscipline cases

The attitude for teachers and students was sought. To get to know the attitude of teachers and students towards guidance and counselling services, the researcher gave a list of statements to which teacher counselors, head teachers and teachers and students were to show their level of agreement to effectiveness of guidance and counselling services in schools. As such, these statements were indicators of the attitude held by teachers and students. The summary of the findings are indicated in the following tables.

Table 3: Level of teacher counselors' agreement on attitude of students and teachers

Item	Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
Believe that guidance and counseling is important	6	100	-	-	-	-
Guidance help deal with indiscipline	6	100	-	-	-	-
Guidance and counseling is better than corporal punishment	2	33.3	4	66.7	-	-
Like to use G & C frequently	2	33.3	-	-	4	66.7
Most students visit guidance and counseling office	-	-	2	33.3	4	66.7

Table 3 reveals that all (6) 100% the teacher counsellors believe that guidance and counseling is important and that guidance and counseling help deal with indiscipline cases. The findings agree with the findings of Mikaye (2012) which concluded that guidance and counselling is important in secondary schools. He further noted that guidance and counselling services offered in secondary schools were educational guidance, career guidance and psychological and social guidance.

On whether guidance and counseling was better than corporal punishment, only (2) 33.3% strongly agreed while (4) 66.7% were undecided. It was not established why majority of the teacher counselors were undecided on their responses on the question. This may imply that the teachers still believe that corporal punishment was better or cannot compare the two. According to Education Act Cap 212 of the Laws of Kenya, corporal punishment was used as a way of dealing with indiscipline in schools. In this act, corporal punishment was inflicted only after a full inquiry on the offender and offence had been made and was administered by the principal or teacher to whom it had been delegated by the principal.

It was further noted that majority of the teacher counselors (4) 66.7% disagree that they did not like to use guidance and counseling program frequently. This indicates that although they agree that the program was important; their attitude towards the program was negative.

The study also noted that (4) 66.7% disagree that most students visit guidance and counseling. This implies that the students have negative attitude towards guidance and counseling program. This concur with the study of Ogoda (2009) which established that factors that hinder the success of counselling intervention other than lack of professionalism of teacher counsellors were poor prior counselling experience and the negative attitudes of students towards counselling.

Table 4: Level of head teachers' agreement on attitude of students and teachers

Item	Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
Believe that guidance and counseling is important	8	100	-	-	8	100
Guidance help deal with indiscipline	8	100	-	-	8	100
Guidance and counseling is better than corporal punishment	8	100	-	-	8	100
Most students visit guidance and counseling office	3	37.5	5	62.5	8	100

The head teachers' responses on the attitude of students and teachers on guidance and counseling services revealed that all the head teachers agree that guidance and counseling services were important. This agrees with the teacher counsellors findings where they all agree on the importance of the program. They all agreed also that guidance and counseling program deals with indiscipline in their schools. This implies that if guidance and counseling programs are well embraced in secondary schools, indiscipline cases will be curbed.

Contrary to the teacher counsellors agreements, all the head teachers agreed that guidance and counseling programs were better than corporal punishment. This agrees with the findings of Njogu (2013) which revealed that after the ban of the cane, guidance and counseling was being used in schools and have proved effective and that Guidance and counseling is being used by teachers and whenever used it is bearing positive results in moulding the character and behaviour of the children.

On whether students visit guidance and counseling to seek the service, only (3) 37.5% agreed while (5) 62.5% were undecided. This means that although the head teachers agree on the importance of the programs, students may not be seeking the services. This may be attributed to the fear of the students to face their teachers or the attitude they had towards the program. The findings are in line with the findings of Mander (2013) which established that although there are several guidance and counselling services offered in schools, most students did not seek for guidance and counselling services that concerns with the changes that are taking place in them.

4. Summary

4.1 Sessions for guidance and counseling programs

The study sought to examine effectiveness of guidance and counselling programs on eradication of indiscipline cases in secondary schools in Bureti Sub-County, Kericho County. The study found out that the majority of the principals, teachers, teacher counselors and students considered guidance and counseling services to be important in secondary schools to deal with indiscipline cases. The study noted that majority 83.3% of the teacher counsellors do not agree that the time allocated for guidance and counseling was adequate. All the teacher counsellors (6) 100% agreed that they do not have time for the programme due to the workload of teaching. The respondents indicated that G & C was not catered for in the school time table like the other examinable subjects and that the teachers' heavy teaching loads did not allow them to have sufficient time for guidance and counseling duties. The students indicated that teachers did not use guidance and counseling because they were busy. This implies that

guidance and counseling program however how important it is, is compromised for other academic activities.

The findings further established all the head teachers (8) 100% and students (1588) 100% agreed that guidance and counseling was better than corporal punishment. It was not established why majority of the teacher counselors (4) 66.7% were undecided on their responses on the question. Contrary to the teacher counsellors agreements, all the head teachers (8) 100% agreed that guidance and counseling program was better than corporal punishment.

4.2 Attitude of teachers and students on guidance and counseling programs on management of indiscipline cases

On the attitude of teachers and students, it was established that majority of the teacher counselors (4) 66.4% disagree that they did not like to use guidance and counseling program frequently. This indicates that although they agree that the program was important; their attitude towards the program was negative. The study established that most students (4) 66.4% do not seek guidance and counseling. It was not established why they do not seek the services. All the head teachers (8) 100% also confirmed that guidance and counseling program deal with indiscipline in their schools.

4.3 Conclusions

1. The study concludes that guidance and counselling is important in secondary schools and was offered in the schools. Guidance and counseling services offered were educational guidance and to deal with indiscipline cases. Although all the schools appreciate the important of guidance and counseling in correction of students, the time allocated for the program was either not available or inadequate. The teacher counselors also had limited time for counseling due to the workload they have.
2. The study concludes that the teachers' attitude though positive, was affected by the students' absence to seek for guidance and counseling services. Therefore, the students' attitude was concluded to be negative. Although the students acknowledge the program, majority did not seek guidance and services. It was not however the main reason for them not to seek guidance and counselling.

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